

Original Research

Impact of Taxpayer Compliance on Revenue Collection: A Case of Mbeya City, Tanzania

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Abstract

The research aims to investigate the effect of taxpayer compliance on revenue collection using Mbeya City as a case study. Examine the degree of compliance, the variables influencing taxpayer compliance, and the relationship between taxpayer compliance and revenue collection. In the study, both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies were used. Data from 50 respondents were gathered via interviews and questionnaires. Multiple regression analysis, content analysis, and descriptive statistics were used to examine the data. The majority of respondents, according to the statistics, believe that taxpayers file returns on time, pay all taxes owed by the deadline, and accurately record their income. Furthermore, the majority of respondents said that tax rates, penalties and fines, tax audits, tax payer attitudes, and knowledge and education all have an impact on municipal taxpayer compliance. Furthermore, the data revealed a substantial link between taxpayer compliance and revenue collection. The study advised that authorities closely assess the impact of taxpayer compliance on tax collecting operations. Furthermore, it is proposed that the tax system give a clear and straightforward guidance on how to fill out tax returns, but also strengthen taxpayer education programs so that people understand their rights and duties as taxpayers.

Keywords: Mbeya City, Revenue Collection, Taxpayer Compliance.

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Introduction

Increasing general compliance with a nation's tax laws and fostering public confidence in the tax system and its administration are the main objectives of a tax authority's compliance activities (Okunogbe & Santoro, 2023). Regardless of the cause administrative errors, taxpayer ignorance, carelessness, recklessness, or deliberate evasion noncompliance with the law is unavoidable. Governments and the publics they serve lose out on tax revenue that is required to provide services to citizens to the extent that these failures take place (Jayawardane & Low, 2016). Taxation is a significant source of income for the government and its administrations; it enables the government to meet its financial responsibilities while also delivering services to the people. Tax systems have evolved throughout the years, owing to the necessity of governments to satisfy the expectations of their citizens (Nurebo *et al.*, 2021).

Tax compliance by taxpayers depends on how taxpayers view the tax systems, taxpayers' understanding of tax laws, the established sanctions such as fines, the expense of complying with taxes, and perceived behavioral control (Bawono *et al.*, 2020). Tax compliance concerns should take into consideration residents' views and societal conventions while carrying out their tax obligations. Tax compliance among taxpayers (citizens) may cease when taxpayers realize that they gain from their tax payments, although the reduction or rise in tax penalties tends to have minor influence on taxpayers' compliance choices (Thuy & Thach, 2022). Tax collection is an important duty in every nation since it provides the government with the required money to support the budget. Taxpayer compliance is a critical component of revenue collection for governments worldwide. It has a direct impact on the government's income generation, which in turn impacts its capacity to provide public services and achieve developmental objectives. This is because collected money is the lifeblood of every government, allowing it to provide important services, infrastructure, and public goods that contribute to the well-being and growth of its people (Hamid *et al.*, 2020).

Tanzania's tax structures originate from the colonial period, when income tax, customs, and excise tax receipts were supervised by the East African High Commissioners. Local Chiefs were obligated to collect taxes on behalf of local governments, while District Commissioners were responsible for collecting personal taxes on behalf of the Treasury. Tanzanian taxpayers provide a growing tax compliance issue to the government, resulting in greater inequities in tax collection. Despite the important importance of revenue collection in urban development, many locations in Tanzania, especially Mbeya City, encounter a number of obstacles in maximizing income. The central problem revolves around the issue of taxpayer compliance. Factors compounding the issue have been evidenced with tax evasion leading. Some individuals and businesses have been noted to engage themselves in tax evasion practices, deliberately underreporting income or concealing assets to reduce their tax liability. This not only deprives the revenue but also creates an uneven tax burden on compliant taxpayers. Non-compliance can result from various factors such as complex tax laws, ineffective enforcement mechanisms, and taxpayer attitudes towards taxation (TRA, 2018).

One critical goal of every country is to earn cash both domestically and outside to pay their national budgets and conduct enormous infrastructure projects. However, earning the necessary cash has become a huge challenge for many governments, particularly emerging countries like Tanzania. Tax income shortfalls have become a serious issue in the majority of developing nations, including Tanzania (Okunogbe & Santoro, 2023). In order to increase revenue collection, most tax administrators find it difficult to maintain a high level of tax compliance, especially among Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) (Deyganto, 2018). Despite efforts to emphasize the significance of taxpayer compliance, many African governments, like Tanzania, continue to struggle to collect enough tax income to sustain necessary expenditures in public services (World Bank, 2023). Understanding the elements that affect compliance and their influence on revenue collection is critical for developing successful tax policy and enforcement measures.

The various studies have been done around the world concerning tax compliance such as Hamid et al., (2020), Jayawardane & Low (2016), Pope & Jabbar (2008) and Okunogbe & Santoro (2023). But Most of the studies have conducted on the factors affecting tax compliance and other studies such as Hamid et al., (2020) and Deyganto (2018), have conducted factors affecting revenue collection. There are few researches on the influence of taxpayer compliance on revenue collection, particularly in Tanzania. Previous researchers in Tanzania did not pay enough attention to this problem. As a result, this research is anticipated to give information about the influence of taxpayer compliance on revenue collection in Tanzania, especially in Mbeya City, this helps to bridge the gap by creating the local sparse data on tax compliance and revenue collection in Mbeya City.

Literature Review

Empirical Review

Researchers across the globe come with different arguments on this topic for example, Ha & Nguyen (2022) stated that, People's decisions to pay taxes may be influenced by more than just the tax rate. Another factor is the overall design of the tax system. Individuals may choose to reveal just a part of their earnings if they believe that their own tax burden is unfair, for instance, if the tax rate on corporate profits is relatively low but the tax rate on their own income is high. In a similar vein, big businesses could often take advantage of tax incentives, which adds to the system's apparent injustice. The tendency of individuals to dodge and avoid paying taxes is greatly influenced by tax rates and the structure of the tax system as a whole. According to study by Pinem (2019), a person's knowledge base has a big impact on how they behave and how that behavior impacts tax evasion. Lower educated taxpayers are more likely to evade taxes because they are less likely to be exposed to and aware of crucial tax compliance information. Some taxpayers have a harder time than others comprehending the complexities of tax information. If taxpayers find it difficult to complete their tax forms, this complexity might result in unintentional noncompliance.

Mohamad *et al.*, (2022), examined the factors influencing Malaysian taxpayer compliance behavior. The study also examined the attitudes and opinions of the respondents about the impact of distributive justice, procedural fairness, and honesty on tax compliance in Malaysia. Research indicates that people's compliance behavior

increases when they get fair and honest treatment from tax officials. Furthermore, it has been shown that tax penalties significantly affect tax compliance. The findings are consistent with the theory that tax authorities may increase compliance by enhancing their communications with taxpayers. Huong & Phuong (2021), examined the elements that affect business tax compliance, using a case study of small and medium-sized businesses in Quang Ninh. According to a poll of 217 taxpayers, societal standards have an indirect impact on taxpayers in terms of tax fines and penalties. Furthermore, the research found that tax compliance is significantly impacted by government honesty. This study's contribution may assist tax authorities in creating more efficient and cost-effective methods of improving taxpayer compliance.

According to Hoa *et al.*, (2019), elevated penalties just increase the risk of tax evasion for taxpayers and ought to discourage them from doing so. The empirical evidence does not consistently support the deterrent impact of penalties. A rise in fines may have the unintended consequence of encouraging greater tax evasion. In order to improve tax administration, Okunogbe & Santoro (2023) investigate the possible advantages of contemporary technology breakthroughs for African countries. It provides a broad overview of the benefits and drawbacks of the several tax regimes in Africa, such as trade, income, real estate, and consumption taxes. The use of technology to monitor compliance, assist in identifying the tax base, and facilitate compliance is then explored as a way to solve these concerns. Lastly, it provides insights from interviews with leading tax administrators throughout the continent on their actual experiences with employing technology for taxes.

Researchers have highlighted various factors influencing taxpayer compliance and its impact on revenue collection, with regional studies offering critical insights relevant to the Tanzanian context. For example, Kira (2021) explored the effects of tax system design on taxpayer behavior in Tanzania. He argued that the perceived fairness of the tax system plays a crucial role in determining whether individuals comply with tax regulations. If taxpayers perceive the tax system as inequitable, particularly when it favors large corporations over individuals, they are more likely to engage in tax evasion. Similarly, Mwakibinga & Matotola (2020) examined the role of taxpayer education in Mbeya, finding that limited access to tax information significantly impacts compliance levels. Their study revealed that taxpayers with a better understanding of tax laws and procedures were more likely to comply, highlighting the need for targeted taxpayer education programs in Tanzania. Moreover, Mkondya & Kisandu (2019) investigated the relationship between tax penalties and compliance in Dar es Salaam, noting that while penalties can deter tax evasion, excessive fines may lead to increased non-compliance due to the fear of punitive measures. They suggested a balanced approach to penalties that considers both deterrence and taxpayer cooperation.

In addition, a study by Mbilu (2022) in Mwanza City emphasized the role of government transparency and accountability in fostering taxpayer compliance. The research found that taxpayers are more likely to comply when they perceive that the government uses tax revenues effectively and transparently. This finding aligns with global perspectives on the importance of trust in tax authorities. Finally, Kessy & Urjo (2023) explored the potential of digital tax administration tools in enhancing compliance in Tanzania, particularly in Mbeya. Their study demonstrated that the adoption of digital

technologies, such as electronic filing and mobile tax payments, significantly improves compliance rates by simplifying the tax process and reducing opportunities for corruption.

Theoretical review

The Allingham and Sandmo Theory

Efuntade & Efuntade (2023), said that the government deters tax evasion via audits and a penal system. The cost of breaking the law and evading taxes seems to be too little for a taxpayer to decide against when they think they won't be found out or subject to an audit. When taxpayers feel that the cost of compliance is too high, they will also avoid paying taxes. Complex and intricate tax laws and regulations often encourage tax evasion. People who think their tax rate is too high and punitive will not pay taxes. The degree and combination of taxpayer knowledge, education, and attitude also affect compliance. There is a negative correlation between tax evasion, the possibility of detection, the severity of the penalty, and the major transaction costs associated with tax regulations. Income tax evasion was first introduced by Allingham and Sandmo, who showed how a rational and moral taxpayer might maximize projected value based only on income (Gemmell, 2016). The agent is required to pay penalties depending on the amount of money avoided in the event that they are found. Conflicting income and substitution variables may either raise or reduce tax compliance when the tax rate increases, according to a significant comparative static finding. Substitution impact drives evasion because tax rate raises the marginal benefit of cheating (Sandmo, 2005). On the other hand, evasion is often suppressed by the income effect since a higher tax rate makes the taxpayer feel worse off, which discourages them from taking on more risk. As a consequence, the final outcome is not entirely obvious. But as most current tax laws interpret this, demonstrated that the substitution benefit vanishes when the penalty is applied to the amount of saved taxes. At the first optimum, there is no substitution effect because the penalty for hiding income increases in line with the tax rate. The influence of residual revenue is responsible for encouraging taxpayer dishonesty (Gemmell, 2016). Therefore, better compliance is the ultimate outcome. findings are perhaps the most significant finding in the early literature on tax evasion as they led to a number of noteworthy extensions. Because they are unable to comply with tax laws, SMEs are vulnerable to tax evasion. They must maintain accurate books of accounts and adhere to stringent deadlines. It is in these types of circumstances that tax evasion occurs. The theory is pertinent to our investigation because it addresses many critical elements of tax compliance, such as the knowledge and education penalty rate, the potential for an audit, and the manner in which taxpayers react to changes in tax rates. It does not, however, succeed in giving an exact prediction of taxpayer behavior. The issue is that they don't provide a comprehensive examination of the social and psychological factors that affect compliance and, therefore, revenue collection (Efuntade & Efuntade, 2023).

Methodology

The study was conducted in the Mbeya Region. The area was selected because to its prevalence of tax-related problems, including problems with tax compliance and revenue collection. This study includes both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies since it helps reconcile differences between findings obtained from the two types of

analyses. The case study research methodology was used for this study because it was flexible in terms of data collection methods and cost- and time-effective. The target demographic in Mbeya City consists of taxpayers, government personnel, and tax administrators. The target population for this study area is 110. 50 replied, despite the study's goal of 52 respondents. As a result, the sample consisted of 50 respondents. According to Yamane (1967), the following formula determines an appropriate and sufficient sample size;

$$n = \frac{N}{(1+N(e)^2)}$$

Whereby;

n = sample size,

N = Targeted population = 110,

e = the level of precision (confidence level which is 10%),

n= 52 but study got response from 50 respondents.

The study employed questionnaires and interview data collection methods. The study obtained Questionnaire data from taxpayers. Thus, the senior staffs made the effective use of this data collection technique. Therefore, this research used interview technique since it assisted the researcher to capture inner feelings and facial expression of respondents about the study topic. The researcher used 4 senior staffs out of 8 staffs for the interview because she believes they possess very vital and detailed information concerning the tax compliance and revenue collection. Descriptive analysis, inferential analysis and content analysis was applied in data analysis. The general equation for predicting the dependent variable from the independent factors was:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$$

Where;

Y = Revenue collection,

X_1 = Tax compliance,

β_0 = Co-efficient of the model,

β_1 = Beta Co-efficient of Determination,

ϵ = Stochastic Error Term.

Variables and Measurement

The table below show the operationalization of variable and how variables was measured.

Table 1. Operationalization and Measurement of Variables

Research Objective	Indicators	Type of Data to be Collected	Data Collection tools	Measurement	Methods of Data Analysis
Level of tax payer's compliance	Filing compliance Payment compliance Demographic factors	Primary data	Questionnaires	Likert scale format	Descriptive
Factors influencing tax payer's compliance	Tax rate Penalty and fine Tax audit Tax payers' attitude Knowledge and education	Primary & Secondary data	Questionnaires and interviews	Likert scale and facial expression respectively	Descriptive and content analysis
Effects of taxpayer's compliance on revenue collection	Taxpayer compliance rate Files tax returns on time States the correct income Improvement of revenue collected	Primary & Secondary data	Questionnaires	Likert scale format	Descriptive and regression analysis

Findings and Discussion

This section provides an overview of the study's conclusions about the information gathered and handled in line with its goals.

Level of compliance of taxpayer in Mbeya City

The respondents were asked to state the level of compliance of taxpayer in Mbeya City. The results were grouped on a five-point Likert scale format, ranging from 1. Strong agree 2, Agree 3, Neutral 4, Strong disagree and 5 Disagree. The results are summarized in table 2.

Table 2. Level of compliance

S/N	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
1	Tax payers file returns on time	24	32	18	18	8
2	Tax payers pay the correct amount of taxes owed by the due date	24	38	22	6	10
3	The tax payers state the correct income	10	42	8	24	16

Regarding the statement Taxpayers file returns on time, 24% of respondents strongly agreed, 32% agreed, 18% were neutral, 18% strongly disagreed, and 8% disagreed. These results indicate that while a significant portion of taxpayers comply with filing their returns on time, a notable percentage either remain neutral or express disagreement, suggesting there are compliance issues that might require further investigation or intervention.

Furthermore, regarding whether taxpayers pay the correct amount of taxes owed by the due date, 24% of respondents strongly agreed, 38% agreed, 22% were neutral, 6% strongly disagreed, and 10% disagreed. These findings suggest that while the majority of respondents believe that taxpayers generally comply with paying the correct amount of taxes on time, there is still a notable portion of the population that is either neutral or disagrees, indicating potential issues in full compliance that may need to be addressed.

Additionally, when asked if taxpayers state the correct income, 10% of respondents strongly agreed, 42% agreed, 8% were neutral, 24% strongly disagreed, and 16% disagreed. These results indicate that while a significant portion of respondents agree that taxpayers generally report their income correctly, a considerable percentage either disagree or strongly disagree, suggesting that income misreporting remains a significant concern in Mbeya City. This highlights the need for enhanced verification processes and taxpayer education to improve compliance in income reporting.

Factors that influence taxpayer compliance in the city

The respondents were asked to state the factors that influence taxpayer compliance in the city. The results were grouped on a five-point Likert scale format, ranging from 1. Strong agree 2, Agree 3, Neutral 4, Strong disagree and 5 Disagree. The results are summarized in table below

Table 3. Factors that influence taxpayer compliance

S/N	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
1	Tax rate affect tax compliance	20	36	14	18	12
2	Penalty and fine affect tax compliance	28	30	22	10	10
3	Tax audit affect tax compliance	38	26	14	20	2
4	Tax payers' attitude affect tax compliance	38	16	16	24	6
5	Knowledge and education affect tax compliance	20	24	26	24	6

On the tax rate affects tax compliance, 20% of respondents strongly agreed, 36% agreed, 14% were neutral, 18% strongly disagreed, and 12% disagreed. These results suggest that a majority of respondents believe that tax rates play a significant role in influencing compliance. However, the presence of a notable percentage of respondents who either disagreed or strongly disagreed indicates that other factors may also be at play in determining compliance behavior in the city.

When asked whether penalty and fine affect tax compliance, 28% of respondents strongly agreed, 30% agreed, 22% were neutral, 10% strongly disagreed, and 10% disagreed. These findings suggest that penalties and fines are perceived as significant factors influencing tax compliance, as a majority of respondents agreed with this statement. However, the presence of neutral responses and disagreement indicates that penalties alone may not be sufficient to ensure full compliance, and other factors might also be influencing taxpayer behavior.

For the statement tax audit affects tax compliance, 38% of respondents strongly agreed, 26% agreed, 14% were neutral, 20% strongly disagreed, and 2% disagreed. These results suggest that tax audits are perceived as a significant factor influencing compliance, with the majority of respondents agreeing that audits positively impact compliance behavior. The strong disagreement from 20% of respondents highlights differing perspectives, suggesting that while audits may be effective for some, they are not universally seen as helpful in promoting compliance.

Regarding the statement taxpayers' attitude affects tax compliance, 38% of respondents strongly agreed, 16% agreed, 16% were neutral, 24% strongly disagreed, and 6% disagreed. These results indicate that a significant portion of respondents believe that taxpayers' attitudes play a crucial role in compliance. Nonetheless, the notable disagreement from 24% of respondents suggests varying opinions, implying that while attitudes are influential for some, they are not universally perceived as a determining factor in tax compliance.

Additionally, concerning, knowledge and education affect tax compliance, 20% of respondents strongly agreed, 24% agreed, 26% were neutral, 24% strongly disagreed, and 6% disagreed. These findings suggest that while some respondents recognize the importance of knowledge and education in influencing tax compliance, a significant portion remains neutral or disagrees. This indicates mixed views on the impact of education, with some seeing it as crucial, while others do not consider it as significant in shaping compliance behavior.

Also, throughout the interview, respondents said that;

On explaining the factors that influence taxpayer compliance in the city through interview, one of respondent recorded saying;

“Therefore, the conduct of an individual's reference group that of family, neighbors, and friends may influence their compliance behavior and opinions of the tax system. Therefore, a taxpayer's/her dedication to comply will be

less if they know numerous individuals in organizations significant to him who avoid taxes” (Revenue officer, May 2024).

Also, another respondent on explaining the factors that influence taxpayer compliance in the city said that;

“Reasons for non-compliance include high tax rates, confusing tax policies, corruption, high compliance costs, injustice in taxing, insufficient systems and social services” (Revenue officer, May 2024).

Impact of tax payer compliance on revenue collection in Mbeya City

The respondents were asked to state the impact of tax payer compliance on revenue collection in Mbeya City. The results were grouped on a five-point Likert scale format, ranging from 1. Strong agree 2, Agree 3, Neutral 4, Strong disagree and 5 Disagree. The results are summarized in table 4.

Table 4. Impact of tax payer compliance on revenue collection

S/N	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
1	Revenue is increased	24	36	16	14	10
2	Revenue improves due to the taxpayer compliance rate	28	30	24	8	10
3	Revenue has improved because taxpayers’ files tax returns on time	42	26	6	18	8
4	Revenue has improved because tax payers states the correct income	28	32	12	10	18

Concerning, revenue is increased, 24% of respondents strongly agreed, 36% agreed, 16% were neutral, 14% strongly disagreed, and 10% disagreed. These results suggest that a majority of respondents believe that increased taxpayer compliance contributes to higher revenue collection. However, the presence of neutral and disagreement responses indicates that while there is a general consensus on the positive impact of compliance, there are still differing opinions on its effectiveness in boosting revenue.

Furthermore, regarding revenue improves due to the taxpayer compliance rate, 28% of respondents strongly agreed, 30% agreed, 24% were neutral, 8% strongly disagreed, and 10% disagreed. This indicates that a majority believe increased compliance enhances revenue, although some remain neutral or skeptical.

In addition, the researcher wanted to find out whether, revenue has improved because taxpayers file tax returns on time, 42% of respondents strongly agreed, 26% agreed, 6% were neutral, 18% strongly disagreed, and 8% disagreed. This suggests a strong belief that timely filing contributes significantly to revenue improvement, though there are still some dissenting views.

For the statement, revenue has improved because taxpayers state the correct income, 28% of respondents strongly agreed, 32% agreed, 12% were neutral, 10% strongly disagreed, and no respondents disagreed. These results highlight that many respondents

see accurate income reporting as a key factor in improving revenue, although there is a notable percentage that remains neutral or disagrees.

Regression Analysis

Mbeya City's tax payer compliance and revenue collecting were investigated using regression analysis.

Model fitness: The analysis turned up an R-Square of .656. This figure shows that 65.6% of the variation in the dependent variable Revenue collecting can be explained by the independent variables tax payer compliance. The modified R² of the model was then determined by the research to be .633. Linear regression therefore explains 63.3% of the variation in the data. Given a R square more than 50%, the regression model is sufficient.

Table 5. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.810 ^a	.656	.633	.59483
a. Predictors: (Constant), Tax payer compliance				
b. Dependent Variable: Revenue collection				

ANOVA: The findings reveal Prob>F= 0.000, less than 0.05, and suggest that the general model statistically forecasts the outcome variable noticeably. This suggests that dependent variable that of tax payer compliance has implications on independent variable (Revenue collection).

Table 6. ANOVAa

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	30.944	1	10.315	29.152	.000 ^b
	Residual	16.276	48	.354		
	Total	47.220	49			
a. Dependent Variable: Revenue collection						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Tax payer compliance						

Estimated Model Coefficients: The regression findings based on independent variable revealed a notable positive correlation between tax payer compliance and revenue collecting. Moreover, the findings reveal sig-value of 0.000 is less than 5%, suggesting that statistically significant acceptance of the computed coefficient is possible. Consequently, at a 5% level of significance, we find that tax payer compliance significantly influences revenue collecting.

Table 7. Estimated Model Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	.085	.295		.289	.774
	tax payer compliance	.480	.102	.431	4.724	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Revenue collection

Discussion of Findings

Level of compliance of taxpayer in Mbeya City

The results on timely tax return filing highlights that a majority perceive timely filing positively, yet a substantial minority either remain neutral or disagree. This mixed feedback suggests underlying compliance issues that could benefit from deeper examination. A study by Abdu & Adem (2023) emphasizes that varying taxpayer perceptions and compliance behaviors often necessitate targeted interventions to address and improve overall filing practices, indicating a need for more effective strategies and support systems.

The study indicates that while most believe in general compliance, the presence of neutral and dissenting responses suggests potential gaps in full compliance. Supporting this, a study by Carsamer & Abbam (2023) found that perceived discrepancies in tax payments often reveal systemic issues, highlighting the need for enhanced enforcement and education to address compliance shortfalls and ensure accurate tax payments.

The study reveals that taxpayers report their income accurately. Although a majority believe in correct income reporting, the significant portion of disagreement underscores ongoing concerns about income misreporting in Mbeya City. This discrepancy highlights the need for improved verification processes and enhanced taxpayer education. Hong (2022) supports this, showing that robust verification mechanisms and educational initiatives are essential to addressing income reporting inaccuracies and improving overall tax compliance.

Factors that influence taxpayer compliance in Mbeya city

The study suggests that most respondents perceive tax rates as a significant factor affecting compliance. However, the substantial disagreement indicates that other variables may also impact compliance behavior. Inasius et al., (2020) corroborates this view, finding that while tax rates are influential, factors such as enforcement practices, taxpayer education, and economic conditions also play critical roles in shaping compliance behavior.

The results indicate that a significant portion of respondents' views penalties as crucial for influencing compliance. However, the neutral and dissenting responses imply that penalties alone may not guarantee full compliance. Kasper & Alm (2022) found that while penalties are effective, their impact is often moderated by factors such as taxpayer trust,

enforcement consistency, and overall tax system transparency, highlighting the need for a multifaceted approach to improve compliance.

The study shows that a majority view tax audits as impactful in enhancing compliance. However, the significant disagreement points to varied perceptions about the effectiveness of audits. Hassan et al., (2021) found that while tax audits generally promote compliance, their effectiveness can vary based on factors such as audit frequency, transparency, and taxpayer trust, suggesting that audits alone may not be universally effective in all cases.

The study reveals that many believe attitudes are vital for compliance. However, the notable 24% disagreement indicates that attitudes may not be universally seen as a key factor. Supporting this, a study by Musimenta (2020) found that while taxpayer attitudes significantly influence compliance, their impact varies depending on other factors such as enforcement practices, socio-economic conditions, and perceived fairness of the tax system.

The study results show that a mixed perception of the role of education in compliance, with some respondents valuing it as crucial, while others do not. Nasution et al., (2020) supports this view, highlighting that while education can enhance tax knowledge and compliance, its effectiveness varies. The study notes that factors such as the quality of education, its relevance, and combined enforcement strategies also play significant roles in shaping tax compliance behavior

Influence of tax payer compliance on revenue collection in Mbeya City

The study indicates that a general belief that improved compliance boosts revenue, yet the notable neutral and dissenting responses reflect differing opinions on its effectiveness. Ernest et al., (2022), found that while higher compliance generally enhances revenue, the extent of this impact can vary based on factors such as tax system efficiency, economic conditions, and enforcement practices, indicating that compliance alone may not guarantee significant revenue increases.

The results show that a general consensus that better compliance boosts revenue, though the neutral and dissenting responses highlight some skepticism. A study by Kumi et al., (2023), supports this view, noting that while increased compliance typically leads to higher revenue, the actual impact can be influenced by factors like tax policy effectiveness, administrative capacity, and the economic environment, suggesting that compliance alone may not always translate to proportionate revenue gains.

The study indicates that a strong perception that on-time filing plays a crucial role in boosting revenue. However, the dissenting views reflect that not everyone is convinced of its impact. Hong (2022), supports this notion, finding that while timely tax returns are generally associated with improved revenue collection, the overall effect is influenced by factors such as tax administration efficiency and compliance enforcement strategies, suggesting that timely filing alone may not fully account for revenue improvements.

The results show that a strong belief in the importance of correct income reporting for revenue improvement. However, the neutral and dissenting responses indicate some

uncertainty or differing opinions. Naape (2023), supports this perspective, noting that while accurate income reporting generally leads to better revenue outcomes, its effectiveness can be moderated by factors such as reporting accuracy, enforcement practices, and the overall tax compliance environment.

Conclusions

The results lead the research to infer that taxpayer compliance and revenue collecting are linked. Tax compliance not only increases tax income but also helps the tax system to be more generally effective. Moreover, tax compliance has shown rise as people get more aware of how taxes support public facilities and infrastructure. Greater adherence to tax laws and hence support of revenue collecting operations have resulted from taxpayer compliance increasing understanding on the use of tax monies for basic public necessities. Tax compliance is important as companies and people who pay their taxes help the government to generate its tax income. From balancing the budget to providing products and services to its people, government tax income is vital for many purposes.

Recommendations

It is advised that policymakers carefully assess the effects of taxpayer compliance on tax collecting operations in light of the results. A compromise between upholding tax rules and preserving an atmosphere that encourages taxpayers to comply voluntarily should be sought. To maximize the creation of tax income, improvements to the nation's tax system, such as modifications to tax rates, fines, and penalties, should be considered. It is advised that in addition to improving taxpayer education programs to help people understand their rights and responsibilities as taxpayers, the tax system should provide straightforward instructions on how to complete tax returns. Consequently, the government need to create an environment that fosters the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises while encouraging them to proactively pay taxes. If the government takes significant action to provide a long-term remedy for tax non-compliance, this might be achieved. To be fair, tax administrators should consider tax rates that are reasonable and similar to those of the firms. This is a result of the taxpayers seeing tax rates as a financial burden on their companies.

The study's findings serve as the foundation for tax authorities' efforts to restructure tax administration processes and enhance policy in order to maximize taxpayers' benefits and satisfy revenue targets for the national budget. Additionally, the results of this research may assist tax authorities in creating more efficient and less expensive ways to improve taxpayer compliance.

Author Contributions

Author Contributions as far as the data collection is concerned, Mr. Lewis Charles was mostly involved in preparation of checklist that was used throughout data collection, data collection and data cleaning before the analysis. Dr. Beny Mwenda was mainly involved in revision of the work, analysis and argument of the findings.

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<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Mwenda, B., & Charles, L. (2024). Impact of Taxpayer Compliance on Revenue Collection: A Case of Mbeya City, Tanzania. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 11(11), 1574-1590.</p> <p>DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14032631</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_208648.html</p>	<p>A square QR code located in the bottom right corner of the table, which likely links to the article's online version.</p>